

ANALYSIS OF STYLISTIC CONNOTATION IN THE TEXT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8050046>

Abstract. *In literary texts, in which the main function is artistic, connotation acquires additional prominence. This implies that connotation has to be carefully attended to when translating literature.*

Keywords: *connotation; denotation; connotative equivalent; associations; function; culture.*

INTRODUCTION

Denotation, referential or lexical meaning of a word denote a core meaning of an object, an act, or a quality that is generally used and understood by the users; whereas connotation implies the associations that a word may bring to the hearer's mind according to his cognition and experience that are additional to its literal or dictionary meaning. Some words that have approximately the same denotation may hold different connotations. The words *house* and *home* have a shared denotation of "a dwelling place", but *home* has the additional connotations of

«comfort», «privacy» and «domesticity» that are absent from the word *house*.

MAIN PART

The denotation of the word *snake* in the Advanced English Dictionary is: "a long legless, crawling reptile, some kinds of which are poisonous". As for the connotations associated with the word *snake*, they include «evil» and «danger» as reflected in the idiomatic expression "a snake in the grass. The English word *bus* may connote «low cost» and «convenience» for some people (especially the poor), but may be associated with «discomfort» and «inconvenience» for others who own private cars. It may have the connotation of «school» for many children who go to school by bus. Different scholars have differently tackled connotative meaning. John Stewart Mill as early as 1843 related the term 'connotation' to the attributes or properties that a word connotes in opposition to its denotation (cited in Lyons, 1977, p. 175). Pyle and Allgeo (1970, pp.198-200) consider a word's associations to be restricted to "the senses of all the words with which it is always used", i.e. regardless of its referents. Osgood et al (1971, pp.15-16) focus on the psychological condition of using a word and view connotation as the emotive reactions of the users of language to it. Nida and Taber (1974, pp. 91-94) view connotation in terms of the emotional effects of a word on speakers and the emotional response of hearers. Lyons (1987, pp. 54, 143) states that connotation as a psychological and social aspect of expressive meaning reflects the feelings of language users towards a certain issue or thing, and that words like 'huge', 'enormous', 'gigantic', and 'colossal' reflect the speakers' feelings rather than the things they describe. Palmer (1981, p. 92) views connotation as the emotive overtones that result from different styles and dialects. Hervey, S. & Higgins, Ian (1992) classify connotative meaning into six types: Associative, Emotive, Attitudinal, Reflected, Collocational, and Allusive Connotation. Hatim (1997, p. 228) defines connotation as the "additional meanings that a lexical item acquires beyond its primary, referential meaning". Graddol et al (2005, p. 103) equate connotation with "the associations that words have for

us". Munday (2001, p. 154) states that shifting the ST connotations may sometimes produce a shift in ideology.

Many connotations are well-established and constitute part of the linguistic competence of speakers (Nord, 2005, p. 102). Carter (2004, p. 116) classifies words into core words that are neutral in connotation such as the word *thin*, but a core word may have a synonym that is positive (*slim*) or negative (*skinny*). Connotation is one way in which synonyms may differ (Palmer 1981, p. 89). They are subject to continuous change. Many of the most obvious changes in the English language have resulted from changes in word connotations.

Connotations are affected by the co-texts and contexts. The word *dove* acquires positive connotations from such collocations as : "the dove of peace" , "harmless as a dove"; whereas its synonym *pigeon* has negative connotations as it is associated with such collocations as : "a claypigeon" , "pigeon droppings" , etc (Pyle & Allgeo. 1970, P. 200). The word *liberal* has negative connotation in: "He is too liberal", but has positive connotation in : "He is liberal in an area of dictatorship". The word *bug* can have a positive or negative connotation in different co-texts and contexts:

This room is full of bugs! (negative connotation.) John is as cute as a bug. (positive connotation).

The connotation of a word is also affected by the context of use (setting, occasion, purpose or function, and participants). The word *laser* is admirable among engineers, but many people have negative feelings about it as a result of the medical risks associated with laser technology. That is why advertisers use the *scanner* in advertisements which is a euphemism instead of *laser-using equipment*.

Connotation is not restricted to words only. Morphemes, syntax, sounds, spellings, and even typographical features can all connote certain meanings and have specific intended functions. For example, the suffix *-ish* was neutral as to connotation in the past, but nowadays has acquired unfavourable connotations in such words as *boyish*. The suffix *-ese* (in words like *journalese*, *translationese*, *officialese*) also contains negative connotations. Some grammatical structures too can have certain connotations.

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